

<p>LANGUAGE PERSONALITY PROBLEM IN THE LINGUOPERSONOLOGY</p>		<p style="text-align: center;">Linguistics</p> <p>Keywords: lingvopersonology, linguistic personality, gender, attribute, intraindivid, interindivid, metaindivid, lexicographic method.</p>
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<p>Abstract</p>	<p>This article examines linguistic personality types according to the personal characteristics of the speakers: linguistic personality by social sign, linguistic identity by age types of linguistic personality by gender, types of linguistic personality by nationality, types of linguistic personality by language, dialectal sign according to linguistic types. The following attributes of personality are distinguished in the theory of personalization: intraindivid, interindivid, metaindivid. Inductive, lexicographic, mathematical linguistic methods, method of analysis of the formal characteristic of the text are the most commonly used common-language methods in linguopersonology. In linguopersonology, the inductive method implies a “text-to-author” approach, and the Descriptive, in particular the linguistic description method, explains the separation, classification, structure and function of language units. It is possible to show different features of language units on the basis of lexicographical dictionaries, use mathematical linguistic techniques to characterize individual methods, including the copyright of the text owner, to analyze the length of sentences in the method of formal textual analysis, relationship.</p>
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In the last century, the linguistic unit of world linguistics has been deeply studied in the system-structural aspect and great results have been achieved in this direction. By the end of the 20th and beginning of the XXI century, linguistics had a tendency to study language units in relation to the human factor. At this time there was a suggestion that the human factor was the primary one in the language problem of speech. In particular, it has been scientifically proven that the text, which is the product of human speech, cannot be studied without the person who created it, without its features. This approach to language learning has also completely changed the attitude of his study. As a result, language units began to be examined in terms of the speaker's and perceptions of the linguist's mentality, national and cultural attitudes, age, gender, social status, and occupation. All this paved the way for the emergence of anthropocentric linguistics, a new scientific paradigm that examines the human factor in language. Today this direction has become the main scientific paradigm of world linguistics.

Anthropocentric linguistics differs from its original scientific directions in terms of its object of study and its approach to language studies. However, one cannot ignore the fact that this direction also feeds on all the unusual scientific directions. As a specific language phenomenon is investigated in anthropocentric aspect, of course, the system-structure paradigm deals with the language units separated. Highly appreciating the possibilities of anthropocentric linguistics, Safarov wrote: “The system-structural paradigm eliminates the disadvantages of the comparative-historical paradigm that arose as a result of the 'atomistic' analysis of language phenomena separately. He did it. The main effect of the system-structural orientation is to prove that language is a systematic phenomenon.

However, these two paradigms have a common disadvantage: the language in which these languages are separated from its owner – man. Attempts to eliminate this defect have led to the creation of pragmatic and cognitive linguistic paradigms” [6, p. 35].

It is noteworthy that even system-structure linguistics has completely ignored the human factor in the study of language phenomena. There are situations in the language where the nature of certain linguistic events cannot be determined without the human factor. For example, without examining the communicative purpose of the speaker, it is not possible to determine the type of expression according to the purpose of the expression. Or certain phonetic changes in speech sounds cannot be fixed without the speaker. In system-structural linguistics, the solution of such problems, of course, refers to the human factor in language.

The emergence and spread of anthropocentric paradigm in linguistics, and much research in this area has led to the emergence of a number of new dimensions in human language. The study of language in relation to the person who uses it has led to the intersection of linguistics with such disciplines as psychology, philosophy, logic, cultural studies, sociology [9, p.102]. Today, world-class linguistics, such as cognitive linguistics, psycholinguistics, pragmalinguistics, psycholinguistics, linguoculturology, linguopersonology, gender linguistics, sociolinguistics, are emerging as independent disciplines of anthropocentric linguistics.

In the Uzbek linguistics today, the basic concepts of anthropocentric linguistics, such as language personality, linguistic personality, linguistic consciousness, speech status, linguistic reserve, are deeply embedded in the language. In our linguistics certain studies have been devoted to the analysis of pragmalinguistics, linguocultural, cognitive features of language units, gender and social differentiation. Of course, there are a lot of problems that need to be done in these areas, which are the youngest areas of anthropocentric linguistics. One such problem is the study of linguistic personality types in fiction.

The emergence of new theoretical perspectives in the linguistic conception of speech makers and perceptions has given rise to the emergence of a new field of study – linguopersonology. The linguistic view of the human being as a linguistic person, not simply as a person using language, but as a linguistic person, manifesting his own personality through the language, instilling national-cultural, ethnic identity, preserving the language and passing on to future generations. Consequently, the speech makers and perceptions are object of study of linguopersonology.

Personality problems are also addressed in areas other than linguistics. Person is the object of study of various sciences such as psychology, personology, philosophy. In psychology, for example, when one examines the mental state of an individual, it examines the formation of a person as an individual, that is, his personification. According to N.G.Voronova, the individual, social subject, individual subject are all stages of humanization. An individual is a "product" born by a parent, and a social subject is a product of "environment and conditions".

A person as an individual entity is a product of "his or her own", which means "causa sui", that is, "his or her own cause." is. Therefore, personalization is the formation of a person as a subject of his or her own life [1, p. 11].

In the 1980 years Russian psychologists A.V.Petrovsky and V.A.Petrovsky developed the theory of personalization in social psychology. The basis of this theory lies in the concept of personality.

V.A.Petrovsky distinguished in personality theory the following attributes of personality: intraindivid, interindivid, metaindivid. He concludes that the personality is the quality of the individual and is revealed through the unity of these three attributes. According to the scientist, the intraindividative attribute is an indispensable attribute of the individual. The interindivid attribute means that the identification of the person and his or her existence is done not by the individual alone, but by at least two individuals. The contribution of one individual to the other in the meta-personal attribute is influenced by the effect of changes in his behavior and consciousness [8, p. 40-46].

It is understood that the formation of a person as a person is a subjective process. Therefore, as a person, he is the subject of his life.

For the first time the idea of formation of psychology as a science was put forward by N.S.Trubetsky. In his view, the personality is of a non-repetitive quality and can therefore be the subject of scientific and philosophical research. It examines the general laws of the existence of a person, its relation to the outside world, its relation to the person, its formation as a person. The scientist noted that different problems are involved in these problems, but the need to create a personalized personality-specific science and the absence of this discipline is a gap in scientific thinking [7, p. 106-107].

Personality problems are also explored in literary studies. Literary studies deal with artistic images of individuals or those typical of society. For sociology, the individual has socially distinctive characters, the psychology of the person is the primary, and so on. In linguopersonology, the linguistic role of the individual plays an important role in these areas. It is peculiar that in linguopersonology all the personality traits examined in other areas are studied in connection with his speech.

The problem of linguistic identity in linguopersonology is the main issue. In the analysis of the linguistic picture of the world in certain languages, the study of the linguistic personality is also important. The solution to this problem is inevitably supplementing theoretical knowledge with regard to the linguistic role of the outside world in language. The analysis of the external world in language, and the role of the linguistic person in the language, requires a linguistic approach to the linguistic aspect. It is possible to say that the creation of text in linguistics, the interest of the linguists to explore the reflection of personality traits in the text, necessitated the study of the linguistic aspect of the language.

Based on the linguistic aspect of the text, it is possible to determine the influence of language owners on the use of the language and the external factors involved in the process.

In the last century, there has been much research in linguistics in the world of linguistics. G.I. Bogin has worked in this area to create a speech model and a linguistic personality model that generates and accepts speech. N.V. Melnik tried to differentiate between linguistic and linguistic personology. In his view, personal linguistics studies language, text, and speech activities through personality characteristics. Linguistic personology, on the other hand, is a science of personality, characterized by a theoretical and methodological and clear descriptive nature [5, p. 159-162].

V.P. Neroznak acknowledged in the article "Lingvisticheskayapersonology: k opredeleniyustatusadiscipliny" that linguistic personology has evolved as a science direction [4, p. 112-116]. However, some linguists note that this direction is still in the process of formation. In particular, Y.V. Goritskaya stated that it is a new direction in the formation phase of linguopersonology and therefore its theoretical and methodological apparatus has not been fully developed. According to him, along with the general scientific methods in linguopersonology, it is based on the methodology of linguistic and specialists working in this field, in particular Yu. Structural modeling of V.V. Karaulov. Methods for linguistic reconstruction of Druzhinina and AA Vorobjitova, communicative portraiture of OSIssers, genetic method of portrait by K.F. Sedov [2, p. 64]. According to the scientist, all methods used in linguistic study should be regulated. He used inductive, lexicographical, mathematical linguistic methods, method of analysis of formal characteristic of text as the most commonly used general-purpose methods in linguistics [2].

The inductive method in linguopersonology implies a "text-to-author" approach. Descriptive, in particular, the method of linguistic descriptions, provides an explanation of the principles and functions of the separation, classification, and construction of language units. It is possible to show different features of language units on the basis of dictionaries, lexicographic method. Mathematical linguistics methods are used to define the properties of individual methods, including the copyright of the text owner. The method "Analysis of the formal characterization of the text" involves the analysis of the length of a sentence, the determination of the relation of a particular word to the number of words used in the category.

It is understood that linguopersonology is a multidisciplinary approach and its research methods are different. The use of different research methods in linguopersonology means that its research methods and methods are not yet clearly defined. Other linguists, who have taken this into account, also acknowledge that this direction is not fully formed. According to D. Lutfullaeva, D. Khudoyberganova, "... this direction can be considered as a new direction in the linguistics of the 20th century. Since the development of theoretical and methodological foundations and methods of analysis of the problem of linguistic personality studied in this direction is not complete. Even the different types of analysis used in linguopersonology indicate that this direction is still in its formation phase" [3, p. 36-37].

It turns out that linguopersonology is a new area of XX century linguistics. Therefore, the development of theoretical and methodological bases and methods of analysis of the problem of linguistic personality studied in this direction is not complete. Even the wide variety of analysis methods used in linguopersonology suggest that this direction is still in its infancy.

Consequently, one of the main tasks of linguopersonology is to study the problem of the transfer of personality traits to speech by means of speech, to distinguish between the types of linguistic entities that produce speech and the perception of speech, and to create a linguistic personality typology.

In sum, the formation of linguopersonology is also related to the tendency to study the role of human factor in language. In linguopersonology, language is learned as a social phenomenon that can be realized without a human factor, in speech, in relation to external factors, such as mentality, social status, gender, ethnicity, national cultural identity.

Human is the main organizer of communication. Conversations do not take place outside of the person, so any conversation centered on the concept of a person. However, not only the human, but also the space and time are a prerequisite for the organization of the communication process.

In communication, the linguistic person (s) who communicate information are important to the addressee who receives information about a particular event. For a complete and accurate understanding of reality, information about who is the speaker is also required. As Sh.Safarov noted, the questions of "when" and "where" determine the content of the speech structure accompanied by the question "who". As the scientist reflects on this, he writes: "Human factor plays an important role in speaking, and this factor is one of the indicators that guide communication activities, such as planning, communicating, and implementing strategies. In structural linguistics, we know that the notion of "human factor" applies, but structuralists interpret this concept as "an ideal speaker in the same speech environment" and link it to the definition of "linguistic ability." In the pragmatic view, however, the notion of "human factor" is quite different. Just as communication conditions vary, it does not have the same "perceptions of the speaker and the listener, the purpose, the basis, the means of communication, the aesthetic forms of expression, the subject matter, and the characteristics of the speaker. In addition, these types of social signs are grouped into stable (permanent) and ever-changing groups. It is more important for a pragmatolinguistic analysis of these characteristics than to rely on the concept of "ideal language speaker – speaker".

The "personal-social description" of the speech holder, as stated by the scholar, is important not only in pragmatolinguistics, but also in linguistics. In linguopersonology, a person is given a "personal-social description" through his speech. The main subjects of the communication process are those who make speech and receive speech. Just as the speaker of the speech is the only one or the team, the speakers can be either individual or multiple. Accordingly, the types of speech also differ in the structure of speech.

This distinction leads to the classification of speech according to its creators. Beyond any speech, it is an absolute fact that the composer behind it, whether verbally or in writing, directly reflects the personality traits.

The speech reflects more or less the personality traits of the compiler: mentality, age, occupation, sex, social status, and national and cultural views. The speech can even give an overview of a person's language skills, language skills, and language skills. This distinction in speech also makes it possible to differentiate those who make up the speech. From any text of the communication it is possible to distinguish between the originator and the recipient of the speech, in other words, the user of the language, the person influencing it, and the language receiver. Such a person is expressed in linguistics by the term linguist.

It is understood that the person who makes the speech and the perceptor is the person who, in the process of using this language, influences it with his own personality and breaks the sociocultural national stereotypes. The speech-making and perceptual person with these qualities is a linguist and is the object of study in linguopersonology.

Today linguopersonology is on the path of development as a separate subject of science. Although linguopersonology has not been fully integrated into linguistics as an independent discipline, its object of study, its purpose and objectives, and its research in this area, indicate that it is at the stage of its formation as an independent science branch.

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